

Enhanced Handover Scheme for High Reliability Communications in Integrated NTN/TN

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Abstract—Low-Earth orbit (LEO) satellite networks, being a promising component of non-terrestrial networks (NTN), are meant to provide seamless and ubiquitous global connectivity. However, the high mobility of the LEO satellites results in frequent handovers (HOs), poses significant challenges to maintaining service continuity due to the interruption time experienced during the HO execution phase, which is particularly critical for high reliability communications (HRC). In this aspect, 3GPP proposed the dual active protocol stack (DAPS) HO mechanism for terrestrial networks (TN), a soft HO approach that enables the user equipment (UE) to maintain the simultaneous connection between both the source and target gNBs during the HO execution phase, potentially achieving a zero handover interruption time (HIT). However, DAPS HO is still not supported for NTN in latest 3GPP Release 18, likely due to rapid orbital movement of satellites. Moreover, DAPS HO requires synchronization between source and target nodes during the handover process, a condition that is challenging to identify at all times. Inspired by this challenge, this paper proposes a network-controlled algorithm that enhances the feasibility of DAPS HO in LEO satellites network, thereby minimizing the HIT over a given observation period. The proposed algorithm employs a sequential decision-making process within a predefined window to make the decision on configuring the DAPS HO. Simulation results demonstrate that the proposed approach significantly reduces the HIT, achieving a 80.28% reduction as compared to baseline HO scheme.

Index Terms—DAPS Handover, Non-Terrestrial Networks, LEO satellites, Handover Interruption Time

I. INTRODUCTION

Seamless handover (HO) is a critical requirement in modern wireless communications systems, ensuring uninterrupted service as the user equipment (UE) moves between network nodes. In 3GPP Release 15, HO procedures typically involve the UE disconnecting from the source gNodeB (gNB) before establishing a connection with the target node i.e. break-before-make (BBM) [1]. During this transition, the data transmission halts from both nodes, resulting in an interruption known as handover interruption time (HIT). HIT is particularly critical for high reliability communications (HRC), as a key service category in 5G and beyond, where even minimal interruption can degrade performance and compromise service reliability. This challenge of managing HIT is even more significant for non-terrestrial networks (NTN), especially LEO satellites due to their movement at high relative velocities, causing users to experience the frequent handovers as the satellite moves in and out of the visibility range.

The interruption time reported in 3GPP Release 18, can range in LEO systems from 80 to 250ms depending on differ-

ent factors such as target cell search, physical random access channel (PRACH) acquisition uncertainty, UE processing, fine time tracking of target cell, synchronization signal block (SSB) post processing and the round trip time (RTT) between UE and network nodes [2]. Given this interruption time, effectively managing these frequent HOs is essential for reducing latency and ensuring service continuity during handover.

From the perspective of HO optimization, several HO enhancements have been proposed, mainly for TN. For instance, the conventional HO based on BBM, is not well suited for ensuring robust service continuity in LEO satellite networks, largely due to high HO failures (HOF) rate, resulting from its inability to account for the high mobility of satellites [3]. Extension to this, conditional HO (CHO) is introduced in 3GPP Release 16, aiming to reduce the HO interruption time by reducing the HOFs. However, both schemes still pertain the HIT during the execution stage both in TN and NTN [4], [5].

In support of seamless mobility, multi-connectivity (MC), allows the UE to establish simultaneous connections with multiple radio access network (RAN) nodes [6]. In this setup, a master node handles control functions and key communications, while secondary nodes provide additional resources to the UE, resulting in an efficient network experience. A recent study examines its effectiveness in combination with CHO to enhance the seamless HO and network performance compared to single connectivity (SC) HO scheme [7]. However, above all, MC requires the UE to maintain continuous connection with multiple nodes simultaneously, leading to increased signalling overhead and energy consumption as well.

Besides, 3GPP also proposed the dual active protocol stack (DAPS) as a soft handover mechanism based on make-before-break (MBB) principle. Unlike MC, DAPS approach allows the UE to maintain simultaneous connections with both the source and target gNBs until the random access procedure with the target gNB is successfully completed [4]. In principle, the UE shall be able to keep dual stack containing physical (PHY), medium access control (MAC) and radio link control (RLC) layers with a common packet data convergence protocol (PDCP) entity. Hence, during the handover period, the UE should be able to send and receive data from source and target gNBs and thereby, leading to eliminating the HIT. Investigating existing studies, DAPS has been adopted for TN, such as intelligent DAPS (I-DAPS), which utilizes the deep reinforcement learning (DRL) to reduce HIT and radio

link failure (RLF) for mmWave networks [8]. However, unlike TN, the direct application of DAPS in NTN, particularly for LEO satellites, remains unexplored and is not straightforward. This is primarily due to factors such as high satellite mobility, frequent handovers, and signal propagation delays. Additionally, DAPS HO requires the synchronization between network nodes corresponding to UE during the HO process. This study in [9] covers DAPS HO in NTN and outlines one or more criteria that should be met for its configuration, including factors like physical distance, receive time difference (RTD) or respective round-trip difference (RTT) of UE corresponding to the serving and target gNB. However, it does not address the feasibility of fulfilling these criteria in NTN.

Therefore, this work examines the feasibility of configuring DAPS HO within LEO satellites network. Since, one way to minimize HIT could be maximizing the successful DAPS HOs, this paper proposes a network-controlled algorithm designed to optimize this process. The algorithm operates in a pre-defined search window that continuously monitors network conditions. Whenever the specified criterion is met, the network triggers the DAPS HO, ensuring an adaptive mechanism for improving the DAPS HO efficiency in NTN environment.

The paper is structured as follows. Section II presents the system model design based on LEO satellites and the formulation of objective function. Section III details the network-controlled DAPS HO and the proposed algorithm to maximize its feasibility. Section IV outlines the simulation framework and provides a comprehensive discussion on the results. Finally, the conclusion is drawn in Section V.

II. SYSTEM MODEL

A. System Architecture

Considering the LEO-based NTN framework comprising a set of K orbital planes around Earth. For each orbital plane k , $k \in \{1, 2, \dots, K\}$, there is a set of N satellites serving the region with Earth-fixed beams, thereby the set of satellites in the constellation is denoted as S . Each satellite $s_{i,k}$, $i \in \{1, 2, \dots, N\}$ in orbit k hosts regenerative payload and equipped with at least a full gNB onboard, to support traffic functions and command delivery between satellites to perform HO procedures. The UE located on the ground with geographic position $P_u = (x_u, y_u, z_u) \in \mathbb{R}^3$ is considered visible to satellite with orbital position $P_s(t) = (x_{s_{i,k}}(t), y_{s_{i,k}}(t), z_{s_{i,k}}(t)) \in \mathbb{R}^3$ at time t , when the elevation angle $\theta_{s_{i,k},u}(t)$ between UE and satellite $s_{i,k}$ exceeds a predefined threshold θ_1 . Since the UE movement is assumed negligible compared to relative speed of LEO satellite, thereby the UE is considered stationary.

Assuming that, at time $t = 0$, the UE is initially connected to a satellite, referred to as source satellite $s_{i,k}^{sr}$ and having serving time $T_{i,k}^{sr}$. As the satellite moves along its orbital trajectory during each time slot, the UE identifies a set of candidate satellites that meets the visibility threshold θ_1 for potential connectivity options for HO. Among the available candidate satellites list $S_c \subset S$, it is essential to identify the target satellite, denoted as $s_{i,k}^{tr}$, to ensure reliable handover

while minimizing the risk of radio link failures (RLF), ping-pong effects and most importantly the HIT, during the transition to target satellite.

Since, DAPS HO minimizes the HIT by maintaining simultaneous connections with both the source ($s_{i,k}^{sr}$) and the target satellite ($s_{i,k}^{tr}$), the objective function can be formulated as,

$$\begin{aligned} & \underset{\beta_{\ell,L}}{\text{minimize}} && T_{HIT} = \sum_{\ell=1}^L \beta_{\ell} T_{\ell}^{int} \\ & \text{subject to} && \\ & && \beta_{\ell} \in \{0, 1\} \quad \forall \ell \in [1, L] \\ & && \beta_{\ell} = \begin{cases} 0 & \Rightarrow HO_{\ell}^{DAPS} \\ 1 & \Rightarrow HO_{\ell}^{N-DAPS} \end{cases} \end{aligned} \quad (1)$$

The objective is to minimize the total interruption time T_{HIT} within the observation period $[0, T]$, where L represents the maximum number of handovers occurring during this time-frame, T_{ℓ}^{int} is HIT per handover ℓ and β_{ℓ} is a binary variable, where $\beta_{\ell} = 0$ refers to DAPS HO and $\beta_{\ell} = 1$ corresponds to baseline HO without DAPS ($N - DAPS$). It is noted that the objective can be achieved by maximizing the number of DAPS HOs over baseline HO. However, there is a rule-book that defines the conditions only under which DAPS HO could be feasible, and is defined in next section.

III. NETWORK CONTROLLED HANDOVER PROCEDURE

This section first outlines the control signalling and interaction between UE and the network nodes for network-controlled HO. As formulated in Eq. (1), two scenarios are possible: the network initially prioritize DAPS HO, and if it is not feasible within the defined time interval, it will configure the baseline HO. Subsequently, the algorithm is proposed that aims at identifying the maximum possibility of DAPS HO during the defined service duration.

A. Handover Configuration Steps

The network-controlled HO consists of three phases: preparation, execution and completion, as depicted in Figure 1.

- During the preparation phase, upon triggering the measurement event, the UE sends a *measurement report* (MR) to the source gNB, which primarily contains the list of target satellites and their corresponding elevation angles. The source gNB then consults the ‘‘DAPS HO Rule-Book’’ to assess whether DAPS HO is feasible under the given conditions. Based on this evaluation, source gNB decides whether to configure a DAPS HO or a baseline HO. It then sends a *HO Request* with selected configuration to target gNB for admission control. In response, target gNB sends the *acknowledgment* to source gNB based on received configuration. Subsequently, the source gNB transmits the *RRC Reconfiguration* message to the UE to reconfigure the RRC connection.
- In case of network-controlled DAPS HO, the UE must support the dual protocol stack, allowing it to maintain the source protocol stack with the source gNB during the execution phase while simultaneously configuring and

maintaining the other protocol stacks (e.g., PHY, MAC, RLC) with the target gNB. Then, to synchronize with the target gNB, the UE sends the dedicated random access (RA) *preamble*. Upon receiving the RA preamble, the target gNB responds with an *RA response*. Afterwards, the UE transmits an *RRC Reconfiguration Complete* message to the target gNB. After the *RRC Reconfiguration Complete*, the UE switches its uplink transmission from the source gNB to the target gNB. Since, during these steps, the UE remains connected with the source gNB while establishing a new connection with the target gNB, DAPS HO can achieve a 0 ms of HIT.

In case of baseline HO, UE can maintain only single protocol stack which is associated with the target gNB. Consequently, during the execution of the steps 4 to 5 in Figure 1, there would be an interruption time ranging from 80 to 250 ms for NTN [2], as mentioned earlier.

- During the completion phase, once the UE successfully accessed the target gNB, the target gNB notifies the source gNB by sending the *Handover Success* message. In the final phase, the target gNB sends a *Path Switch Request* to the access and mobility management function (AMF), which subsequently sends a *Modify Bearer Request* to the UPF for DL path switching. Once *Path Switch Request* acknowledgment received by target gNB from AMF, it then sends RRC reconfiguration signaling for *Source Protocol Stack Release*. Following this, the UE releases the source protocol stack of the source gNB.

B. Sequential Handover Algorithm

It can be inferred from Eq. (1) that minimizing HIT over the observation time $[0, T]$ requires the maximal possibility of configuring DAPS HOs over baseline HO. To accomplish this, an algorithm that sequentially evaluates the feasibility of DAPS HO within a predefined search window is proposed. The search window bounds are defined based on two distinct times such as,

$$W = [t_2, t_1] \quad (2)$$

where,

$$t_2 = \min\{t \mid \theta_{s_{i,k},u}^{sr} \leq \theta_2\}, \quad t_2 \in [0, T] \quad (3)$$

$$t_1 = \max\{t \mid \theta_{s_{i,k},u}^{sr} \geq \theta_1\}, \quad t_1 \in [0, T] \quad (4)$$

t_2 is the lower bound of the search window, representing the earliest time when the elevation angle $\theta_{s_{i,k},u}^{sr}$ between source satellite and the UE reaches or falls below the defined threshold θ_2 period. t_1 is the upper bound of the search window, representing the latest time when the elevation angle $\theta_{s_{i,k},u}^{sr}$ between source satellite and the UE is still greater than or equal to the defined threshold θ_1 . DAPS HO can only be configured during this search window and must adhere to additional specific rules defined thereafter.

1) *DAPS Rule-Book*: DAPS HO may encounter packet reordering or, Time-Out issues if synchronization between the source and target satellites corresponding to the UE is not maintained during the HO procedure. To achieve this

Fig. 1. Signalling flow of network-controlled DAPS HO

synchronization, a differential propagation delay criterion is established between the source $s_{i,k}^{sr}$ and intended target $s_{i,k}^{tr}$ satellite corresponding to the UE. To this end, 3GPP defines the maximum receive timing difference γ for new radio (NR) dual connectivity (DC) for different sub-carrier spacings [10]. In this work, we use a $500\mu s$ threshold for $15kHz$ sub-carrier spacing, though it can be adjusted based on the system's capabilities. The differential delay at the UE u from source and target satellite should be within the allowable threshold γ to avoid Time-Out packets, as formulated below,

$$\Delta d_u(t) = \left| \frac{d_{sr,u}}{c} - \frac{d_{tr,u}}{c} \right| \leq \gamma \quad t \in [0, T] \quad (5)$$

where,

$$d_{sr,u} = \sqrt{(R_e + R_h)^2 - R_e^2 \cos(\theta_{s_{i,k},u}^{sr}(t))^2} - R_e \sin(\theta_{s_{i,k},u}^{sr}(t)) \quad (7)$$

$d_{sr,u}$ is the slant range from source satellite to the UE, and a similar expression can be defined for target satellite to UE, R_e refers to the radius of Earth, R_h is the satellite altitude, $\theta_{s_{i,k},u}^{sr}(t)$ is in radians, and c represents the speed of light.

Besides maintaining an allowable differential delay between the two satellites, another critical factor for DAPS HO is

Fig. 2. System model and parameter description for DAPS HO.

ensuring low-latency switching. To achieve this, the DAPS HO process can be optimized by strictly limiting it to Xn-based HO, involving only satellites connected via inter satellite links (ISL). This approach can effectively minimize the control signalling overhead and maintains the UE session continuity without excessive propagation delays. Even for baseline HO, in this work, the priority (not constraint) is given to target satellite linked via ISL.

For each satellite $s_{i,k}$, it is envisaged that four permanent ISLs (P-ISLs) can be established: two within the same orbital plane (Intra-OP ISLs) and two linking to adjacent orbital planes (Inter-OPs ISLs) as shown in Figure 2, and represented as $\xi = \{s_{i-1,k}, s_{i+1,k}, s_{i,k-1}, s_{i,k+1}\}$ [11]. Hence, Eq. (5) is now constraint to the target satellite $s_{i,k}^{tr} \in \xi$ for DAPS HO and becomes,

$$\Delta d_u^{P-ISL}(t) \leq \gamma \quad t \in [t_2, t_1] \quad (8)$$

$$\theta_{s_{i,k},u}^{sr}(t) < \theta_{s_{i,k},u}^{sr}(t-1) \quad (9)$$

The constraint in Eq. (9) ensures that the source satellite is nearing the end of its serving time. Two additional rules apply to both DAPS HO and baseline HO,

$$\theta_{s_{i,k},u}(t) \geq \theta_1 \quad t \in [0, T] \quad \forall \ell, \forall s_{i,k} \in N_k \quad (10)$$

Eq. (10) represents the basic visibility constraints, where a satellite (source or target) is considered visible only when its elevation angle exceeds or equal to the defined visibility threshold θ_1 .

$$T_{s_{i,k},u}^{sr}(t) < T_{s_{i,k},u}^{tr}(t) \quad t \in [0, T] \quad \forall \ell, \forall s_{i,k} \in N_k \quad (11)$$

$$\theta_{s_{i,k},u}^{tr}(t) > \theta_{s_{i,k},u}^{tr}(t-1) \quad t \in [0, T] \quad \forall \ell, \forall s_{i,k} \in N_k \quad (12)$$

Eq. (11) ensures that the remaining serving time of target satellite must be greater than that of the source satellite at the moment HO becomes feasible, which can be evaluated using Eq. (12). It is highly likely that, DAPS HO can occur back and forth in consecutive time slots. The constraint defined in Eq. (11) also ensures avoid this ping pong impact.

This concludes the rule-book for the feasibility of DAPS HO with the following rules to be met simultaneously within

1 Sequential Handover Algorithm

- 1: **Input:** UE geographic position P_u , satellite orbital positions P_s , elevation angle $\theta_{s_{i,k},u}(t)$ corresponds to the UE.
- 2: Initialize three sets with zeros: HO_{DAPS} , HO_{N-DAPS}^{P-ISL} , HO_{N-DAPS}^{NP-ISL} .
- 3: Define the thresholds θ_2 and θ_1 for sequential search window.
- 4: **Output:** Handover to target satellite $s_{i,k}^{tr}$ either with DAPS or Baseline HO.
- 5: **Assumption:** At time $t = 0$, UE is connected to a random satellite with $\theta_{s_{i,k},u}(t) > \theta_1$
- 6: **for** $t = 1$ **to** T **do**
- 7: **if** $\theta_{s_{i,k},u}^{sr}(t) > \theta_1$ **and** $\leq \theta_2$ **then** $\triangleright t \in [t_2, t_1]$
- 8: Find the set ξ (satellites with Permanent ISL)
- 9: **if** $\theta_{s_{i,k},u}^{sr}(t) \leq \theta_1$ **then**
- 10: Prioritize the P-ISL satellite satisfying eq. (11)
- 11: $HO_{N-DAPS}^{P-ISL} \leftarrow +1$
- 12: $s_{i,k}^{sr} \leftarrow s_{i,k}^{tr}$ \triangleright Target satellite is now new source satellite
- 13: **continue** \triangleright Skip to next iteration
- 14: **Otherwise if** $\xi = \emptyset$, choose NP-ISL satellite satisfying eq. (11)
- 15: $HO_{N-DAPS}^{NP-ISL} \leftarrow +1$
- 16: $s_{i,k}^{sr} \leftarrow s_{i,k}^{tr}$
- 17: **continue**
- 18: **end if**
- 19: Calculate the differential delay $\Delta d_u^{P-ISL}(t)$ of satellites in ξ (if available), prioritizing the one satisfying eq. (11)
- 20: **if** $\Delta d_u^{P-ISL}(t) \leq \gamma$ **and** $\theta_{s_{i,k},u}^{sr}(t) \leq \theta_{s_{i,k},u}^{sr}(t-1)$ **then**
- 21: $HO_{DAPS} \leftarrow +1$
- 22: $s_{i,k}^{sr} \leftarrow s_{i,k}^{tr}$
- 23: **else**
- 24: **continue**
- 25: **end if**
- 26: **end if**
- 27: **end for**

the window W , i) DAPS HO is only feasible for satellite connected via permanent ISL (P-ISL), ii) The differential delay ($\Delta d_u^{P-ISL}(t)$) between the source and intended P-ISL target satellite must be less than or equal to γ , iii) The remaining serving time of target ISL satellite must be greater than that of the source satellite at the moment HO becomes feasible, as in Eq. (11). If multiple candidates meet the DAPS HO feasibility conditions, the algorithm selects the one with lowest elevation angle, optionally considering additional factors such as satellite load, network congestion and link quality.

If any of the conditions is not met, the baseline HO will be executed with the priority given to satellite linked via permanent ISL. Otherwise, the UE will hand over to the non-permanent ISL (NP-ISL) satellite satisfying Eq. (12). The algorithm is summarized in Algorithm 1.

IV. SIMULATION FRAMEWORK

This section comprises two parts: the first part outlines the satellite constellation parameters, and the following one comprehends the performance analysis based on proposed algorithm.

A. Constellation Simulation

The Starlink-based LEO satellite network is simulated using Walker-Delta configuration, consisting of 1584 satellite at an altitude of 550 km, as specified in [12]. It is assumed that the UE generates a measurement report at a periodicity of 160 ms, providing updates on observed satellite parameters. The simulation duration is set to cover one complete orbital period, i.e. 96 minutes, ensuring the comprehensive and fair performance

TABLE I
SUMMARY OF SIMULATION PARAMETERS

Parameters	Values
Constellation	Starlink
Configuration	Walker-Delta
No. of Satellites	1584
Inclination	53°
Orbital Planes	72
Altitude	550 km
Simulation Duration	96 minutes
Sampling Granularity	160 ms

evaluation. In this work and without loss of generality, the phasing factor (PF) is set to 27, as it provides spatial separation of satellites in adjacent planes, and increases the likelihood of the satellite connected via permanent ISL being available. The overall simulation parameters are summarized in Table I.

B. Performance Analysis

After establishing the simulation environment, this subsection assesses the effectiveness of the proposed sequential algorithm in minimizing HIT by maximizing the feasibility of DAPS HO. As depicted in Figure 3, the HOs are categorized into three types: DAPS HO, followed by HO to a satellite connected via permanent ISL (P-ISL) but without DAPS, and if neither of these is feasible, HO to a satellite with non-permanent ISL (NP-ISL). The performance is evaluated against two traditional methods in terms of number of HOs and the average serving time initiated by corresponding HO.

1) *Elevation Angle Based HO (EAH)*: The first benchmark follows a criterion where the UE is initially connected to the satellite with the largest elevation angle. The HO is considered feasible for the satellite that satisfies the following condition,

$$\theta_{s_i,k,u}^{tr} > \theta_{s_i,k,u}^{sr} + \theta_{off}, \quad (13)$$

where θ_{off} is the offset parameter, which is set to 4°. This value empirically provides the minimum number of handovers and achieve zero RLFs [3].

2) *Serving Time Based HO (STH)*: The second benchmark operates under a similar condition as described in Eq. (13), but with the added constraint defined in Eq. (11), where the remaining serving time of target satellite must exceed that of source satellite when the HO becomes feasible. This criterion further reduces the number of HOs, as shown in Figure 3. Besides, as seen in Figure 3, the proposed sequential search algorithm outperforms the both methods in terms of number of handovers and significantly enhances the feasibility of DAPS HO. The search window is defined for different values of θ_2 , while θ_1 and γ are kept constant at 30° and 500 μ s, respectively. For the shorter window, $\theta_2 = 33^\circ$ and $\theta_1 = 30^\circ$, the algorithm is able to identify the ratio of DAPS HO over the P-ISL and NP-ISL HOs. It is noted that as the window expands by increasing θ_2 , the likelihood of identifying the DAPS HO also increases. Given the satellite constellation configuration here, the algorithm achieves the maximum number of DAPS HOs when $\theta_2 = 40^\circ$. However, the NP-ISL HOs in Figure

Fig. 3. The number of handovers as a function of θ_2 , when $\theta_1 = 30^\circ$ and $\gamma = 500\mu$ s

Fig. 4. Average serving time per connection initiated by different handover types as a function of θ_2 , when $\theta_1 = 30^\circ$ and $\gamma = 500\mu$ s

3, cannot be avoided due to the unavailability of any target satellite connected via permanent ISL at the time when HO becomes feasible.

Figure 4 illustrates the average serving time per connection initiated by DAPS, P-ISL and NP-ISL HOs. Compared to conventional HO schemes, EAH exhibits a lower average serving time. Interestingly, STH scheme demonstrates a comparable average serving time to this sequential search window algorithm. This is because both STH and the newly proposed approach satisfy the constraints in Eq. (11), which prioritize selecting satellite with higher serving times, a consideration not accounted for in EAH scheme.

Additionally, the average serving time initiated by P-ISL handovers is typically lower compared to the other handovers in the proposed scheme as window expands. Since the P-ISL HO becomes feasible only when the source satellite is nearly disappearing, and it is uncommon for multiple P-ISL satellites to be available simultaneously, thereby the ability to select one that satisfies Eq. (12) is limited. Similarly, the serving time initiated by DAPS gradually increases as the search window

TABLE II
PERFORMANCE ANALYSIS USING DIFFERENT EVALUATION METRICS

Methodology	θ_1	Number of Handovers			Average Serving Time (minutes)			*Total Interruption Time (T_{HIT}) (seconds)	Maximum Uninterrupted Service Time (minutes)	Maximum Consecutive DAPS HOs
EAH	30°	71			1.352			5.680 – 17.750	1.352	0
STH	30°	40			2.400			3.200 – 10.000	2.400	0
	$[\theta_2 - \theta_1]$	DAPS	P-ISL	NP-ISL	DAPS	P-ISL	NP-ISL			
Sequential Window	33° – 30°	14	10	14	2.322	2.441	2.707	1.920 – 6.000	7.351	2
	35° – 30°	18	6	14	2.436	2.303	2.654	1.600 – 5.000	7.526	2
	40° – 30°	24	0	14	2.514	0	2.436	1.120 – 3.500	15.033	5

*Total Interruption time T_{HIT} is relevant to T^{int} i.e. 80 – 250ms, and number of non-DAPS HOs.

length expands. This is because, as mentioned earlier, the likelihood of DAPS HO increases with the window widening, resulting in an earlier handover to a P-ISL target satellite. For instance, the handover occurs at $\theta_2 = 40^\circ$ rather than near 30° , as seen with P-ISL HOs.

One key aspect is maximizing DAPS HO in order to minimize T_{HIT} , Table II presents the total minimum and maximum T_{HIT} for different values of $\theta_2 - \theta_1$. The proposed algorithm improves the minimum and maximum T_{HIT} by 80.28%, when achieving the maximum DAPS HOs, i.e. $\theta_2 = 40^\circ$, compared to EAH scheme and 65% compared to STH scheme.

Another important consideration is evaluating the occurrence of consecutive DAPS HOs to maintain uninterrupted service continuity, thus avoiding disruption caused by non-DAPS HO in-between. In essence, the second last column of Table II, provides the “maximum uninterrupted service time”. To illustrate, when $\theta_2 = 40^\circ$ and $\theta_1 = 30^\circ$, the average serving time initiated by DAPS HO is 2.514 minutes, and, there are maximum 5 consecutive DAPS HO appear during the observation time $[0, T]$, ensuring that the connection remain uninterrupted for approximately 15 minutes despite the HOs.

V. CONCLUSION

The paper enhances the HO scheme to support HRC services by enabling seamless communication. Specifically, the improvements focus on maximizing the feasibility of DAPS HO for LEO satellite network, which can achieve a zero HIT by allowing simultaneous connections with both the source and target satellites during the HO execution stage. However, the feasibility of DAPS HO in NTN, particularly in LEO satellite, faces challenges due to the factors such as high satellite mobility, unsynchronized propagation delays of source and target satellite corresponding to the UE at the time of HO, among others. Hence, to enable DAPS HO, a network-controlled approach is introduced, which sequentially evaluates the DAPS HO feasibility based on predefined rules within specified window. The performance of the proposed approach is evaluated through simulations and compared against two conventional HO methods. The results demonstrate that the

proposed approach effectively eliminates the total HIT over an observation period, thereby significantly enhancing the network’s ability to support the HRC applications.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

Part of CTTC researchers work is funded by Spanish national project SOFIA PID2023-147305OB-C32 funded by MICIU/AEI/10.13039/501100011033 and by FEDER/UE.

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